

Screening for Externalising Behaviours of adolescents in a school setting.

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Abstract-Aim of the current study was to screen students aged between 13-15 years of age, for externalising behaviours, who were not yet identified by the existing systems such as school counsellors and health system. Studies from India that looked in to externalising behaviour in such a population are sparse, to the best of our knowledge. A total of 833 students, between 13 and 15 years of age, from three mainstream government schools, from semi urban background were screened with the help of their class teachers using behavioural criteria and standardised tools. Teachers identified 68 students who showed externalising behaviours who were then further screened using Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ). Accordingly, 32 students were identified to have hyper activity symptoms and conduct symptoms above cut off level. They were included as “students having externalising behaviours in school context”. Thus 3.8% of the children attending a mainstream school were found to have externalizing behaviours. Their strengths identified were adequate prosocial skills and good peer relationships. Boys had a very high preponderance of externalising behaviours which indicates the need for gender sensitive interventions.

Key words-Externalising behaviours, main stream school, behaviour problems, strengths, behaviour profile

1.INTRODUCTION

Severe behavioural problems during childhood years are often precursors of more serious psychiatric problems of adult hood. According to World Health Organisation’s report, ^[1] 10-20% of children and adolescents experience mental disorders. A systematic review of the literature^[2] in PubMed, PsycINFO, and EMBASE for prevalence studies of mental disorders among community samples of children and adolescents showed that mental disorders affect a significant number of children and adolescents worldwide. Various mental disorders have trajectories that can be dated back to childhood.^[3] Studies indicate that the prevalence of childhood psychiatric disorders is much higher than known data.

Mental health research has identified the importance of externalising behaviours long back. There were various studies in the past to understand the nature of externalising behaviours in children and adolescents. A 40 year follow up study,^[4] conducted among a national cohort of UK, in 2009 showed that adolescents who exhibit externalising behaviour go through a multitude of problems that adversely affect them, their families and society throughout their adult life. The impact of externalising behaviour in the individual's life has been unequivocally established by various other studies too. This warrants a more in-depth understanding of these behaviours which will in turn aid in better management.

Kjeldsen et al^[5] studied the trajectory of externalising behaviour in a cohort of children (community sample from Norway) from infancy till early adolescence. They concluded that externalising behaviour can be classified into 5 major classes; high stable(18%), high childhood limited(5%), medium childhood limited(31%), adolescent onset(30%) and low stable(16%). Highest percentage was adolescent onset(30%).

It is a well established fact that externalising behaviours in adolescence lead to various problems in adult life such as addiction and antisocial behaviours. Though there is literature available from the West, Indian studies are sparse. There were studies from India, which has investigated behavioural problems in general, but not specifically externalising behaviours. Prevalence of behaviour problems reported in schools ranged from 22.7%^[6] to 23.3%^[7] As the socio cultural factors play a major role in the manifestation of externalising behaviours, it will be important to explore the behavioural characteristics of children exhibiting externalising behaviours from Kerala, India.

II. AIM

Aim of the study was to explore the psychological characteristics of children studying in mainstream school, who showed externalising behaviour in school context; and who were not yet identified by the existing systems such as school counsellors and health system.

III.METHOD

Students of 3 main stream government schools, from semi urban background were screened with the help of their class teachers. A total of 833 students were screened from these three different schools. Students of 8th and 9th standard classes (13 year-14 year old) were screened. All these children were from lower socioeconomic status, and from semi urban background.

Screening was done at two levels: an initial screening using behavioural criteria and a later screening using SDQ-TF. Initial screening was according to behavioural criteria given to the teachers. Teachers were asked to identify students who were restless or disruptive in the class during most of the working days. Children having Intellectual Disability, Pervasive Development Disorder, severe Attention Deficit Hyper Activity Disorder and Learning Disability were excluded from the study. These children were already identified by the special teachers of the school.

Once the teachers identified student using behavioural criteria, these students were rated using the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire -teachers form((SDQ-TF).

The Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ-TF) is a brief behavioural screening questionnaire. It includes two parts; part A and part B

A) 25 items on psychological attributes; some positive and others negative. These 25 items are divided between 5 scales:

1) emotional symptoms (5 items)

2) conduct problems (5 items)

3) hyperactivity/inattention (5 items)

4) peer relationship problems (5 items)

5) prosocial behaviour (5 items)

The scales 1) to 4) are added together to generate a total difficulties score (based on 20 items)

B) An impact supplement

This part of the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ-TF) asks whether the respondent has a problem, and if so, enquires further about chronicity, distress, social impairment, and burden to others.

Researcher familiarised the teacher with Strength and Difficulties Questionnaire(SDQ-TF). Teachers were chosen who are in-charge of the class and had a minimum of three months familiarity of these students. Teachers rated their students using SDQ-TF.

IV. RESULTS

Students from 3 three government aided schools, belonging to 8th and 9th standard, from semi urban background were selected for the study. There were a total of 833 students. Class teachers identified 68 students who showed externalising behaviours. These 68 shortlisted children were then further screened using Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ-TF). After the second screening, 32 students were identified to have hyper activity symptoms above cut off, conduct symptoms above cut off and associated peer problems. They were included as “students having externalising behaviours in school context”. Thus 3.8% of the children attending a mainstream school, not otherwise identified by existing systems such as school counsellors or health systems, were found to have externalizing behaviours.

Further analysis showed that out of these 32 students,53 percentage had very high range of conduct problems, 28 percentage had high range of conduct problems and19 percentage had above average range of conduct problems.

Among the students who showed externalising behaviours, 38 percentage of them had severe problems in hyperactivity and inattention, 31 percentage had high range of problems in hyperactivity and inattention and 31 percentage had some difficulty in hyperactivity and inattention.

Out of 32 students, 63 percentage had slightly lower peer problems, 22 percentage had low scores in peer problems and 16 percentage students had very low peer problems.

In Impact scale, 38 percentage of the students scored close to average. 28 percentage had slightly raised scores, 9 percentage had high scores and 25 percentage students had very high scores. This indicated that even though all these children had externalising behaviours, it had not impacted their immediate milieu or other areas such as studies and extracurricular activities significantly at this age. It may be such that the difficulties will start to have more impact in later stages of life. So intervening at this point may prevent further damage to their future life.

In prosocial scale, there was more or less even distribution of these 32 students among the various ranges. 25 percentage students had close to average score showing that they have prosocial skills like other non-problematic children in their class. 31 percentage had slightly higher prosocial skills scores and another 25 percentage had high scores and rest of the 19 percentage students had very good prosocial skills. This might be an indication that in school context, many children with externalising problems have good prosocial skills to compensate their problematic behaviour. They show acceptable behaviour towards teachers.

Of these 32 students, 87 percentage had very high scores in total difficulty thus confirming the presence of externalising behaviour as per SDQ-TF rating.

TABLES

TABLE I: SEVERITY IN TERMS OF FREQUENCY AND PERCENTAGE ,OF EACH ATTRIBUTE AS MEASURED BY SDQ-TF

Severity	Attributes	ES	CS	HS	PPS	IS	GT	PSS
0	Count	14				12	1	8
	Percentage	43.75				37.5	3.13	25
1	Count	5	6	10	20	9	2	10
	Percentage	15.63	18.75	31.25	62.5	28.13	6.25	31.25
2	Count	8	9	10	7	3	1	8
	Percentage	25	28.13	31.25	21.88	9.38	3.13	25
3	Count	5	17	12	5	8	28	6
	Percentage	15.63	53.13	37.5	15.63	25	87.5	18.75

*ES-Emotional Scale, CS-Conduct scale, HS-Hyper activity scale, PPS-Peer problem scale, IS-Impact scale, GT-Grand total, PSS-Prosocial scale.

On calculating the mean and variance of the attributes, hyper activity scale and grand total had the highest means.

TABLE 11 SHOWS THE MEAN AND VARIANCE OF THE ATTRIBUTES AS MEASURED BY SDQ-TF

Variable	Mean	SE Mean	StDev
ES	3.625	0.38	2.152
CS	5.375	0.332	1.879
HS	8.25	0.238	1.344
PPS	4.375	0.184	1.04
IS	1.594	0.342	1.932
GT	22.781	0.872	4.93
PSS	4.563	0.373	2.109

*ES-Emotional Scale, CS-Conduct scale, HS-Hyper activity scale, PPS-Peer problem scale, IS-Impact scale, GT-Grand total, PSS-Prosocial scale.

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The graph 1 depicts the mean of the attributes as measured by SDQ-TF

V. DISCUSSION

Teachers were able to identify children with externalising problems using a simple behavioural criteria and a brief questionnaire (SDQ TF). These were students who were not yet identified by the existing health systems. All the students identified were boys. Thus boys had a very high preponderance of externalising behaviours which indicated the need of gender sensitive interventions.

833 students between the age range of 13 -15 years, attending mainstream school from a semi urban area, were screened for externalised behaviours in the school context. Screening was done by teachers. Around 4 % of these children were reported to have externalising behaviours. A meta analysis^[7] showed a prevalence of 23.3% of psychiatric disorders among school going children. Study^[6] done in a similar sample found out that 22.7% of children showed behavioural, cognitive or emotional problems.

An exploratory study done by the same researchers,^[8] among students of a mainstream school found that highest percentage of children having scores in the abnormal range was in conduct problems. In another study,^[9] in a similar sample found that 10% had personality and behaviour disorders. The present study looked into externalising behaviours only and so the percentage would be less, as expected. All the identified cases were boys, which was in line with the findings of higher prevalence of externalising behaviour in boys.^[7]

Prevalence study done in India found that 20 out of 186 children had a psychiatric disorder, giving an annual incidence rate of 18/1000/yr.^[9] The prevalence rates of childhood psychiatric disorders in Kerala was found to be 9.4 % .^[10]

Of the 32 boys who met the criteria for externalising behaviours according to Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ-TF) cut off scores, majority had very high scores on conduct symptom scale. Conduct symptoms were easily identified by teachers in school setting. These students also had a

preponderance of very high scores in hyper activity scale. This goes in line with the previous findings,^[11] that hyper activity and conduct symptoms co-occur.

However, these children didn't have much difficulty in peer relationships. There may be multiple reasons for this. It could be because some of the perceived conduct like symptoms might be a part of gang activities, which ironically helps in peer acceptance. Also peer problems may not be as obvious as hyper activity and conduct behaviours when perceived and rated by teachers.

Study indicated that though these children had hyper activity and conduct symptoms, they had reasonably good peer relationships and prosocial behaviour. This has good prognostic value in management of these children.

VI. STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Sample was homogenous in terms of socioeconomic variables and these variables are representative of most of the student population in Kerala.

Current study explored the behaviour of students solely on the perception of teachers. Data from various sources such as parents report, self reports etc will add more strength to a study like this.

VII. IMPLICATIONS:

In a highly literate state like Kerala, almost all the children attend schools. Majority of their time is spent in school than at home. School and teachers are a major and integral part in their psychosocial development. This study shows that teachers can be trained to identify problem behaviours better using standardized screening instrument. Though this study looked solely on teachers' perception, it is nonetheless a vital source. Findings can be used to understand how teachers perceive the problems and strengths of their students in a school context. This can be later translated into skills training when devising school mental health programs.

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